

Amoghvarsh '12'

First Solo Exhibition of

Digital Artworks By

Dr.Tripti Singh

From - 19-25 Dec 2012

Terrace, Jehangir Art Gallery.

Mahatma Gandhi Road, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India 400 001

The Guru who cuts down the shackles of ignorance of a disciple and lets them soar into the vast open skies of truth.

Prof. Margie Beth Labadie, Dr. John Antoine Labadie and Prof. Bhawani Shanker Sharma

Message from: Prof. Bhawani Shanker Saharma

Dr. Tripti Singh is a promising artist who has a keen interest in the area of Digital Art. She is very good at learning new techniques and skills.

Dr. Singh has explored many techniques and tools used in the various digital art making processes and she has mastered many of these digital tools for her own artistic purposes. Her creative and imaginative skills are quite evident in her recent digital prints which showcase a vibrant use of colors. She has participated in both international and national exhibitions. I have seen the growth in her digital artwork as it has developed over the years. She is also a good photographer.

Prof. Bhawani Shanker Sharma,
Chairman, Rajasthan Lalit Kala Akademi, Jaipur.

Message from: Dr. John Antoine Labadie

Dr. Tripti Singh is a person of many and varied talents and skills: scholar, academic researcher, visual artist, scientific visualizer, photographer, author and digital arts innovator. I have known Tripti Singh since 2005 and, as such, my perspective on the person and her art has breadth, depth and detail. I have been fortunate to have experienced Dr. Singh's artistic and scholarly growth as an advisor to her PhD program and a collaborator on numerous academic and artistic projects.

Through her wide ranging artistic investigations and tireless studio practice Dr. Singh has conducted a significant and ambitious program of personal discovery. Her energetic efforts have produced a large number of innovative and visionary artworks including the stunning imagery presented in her first solo exhibition Amoghvarsha '12. The artworks in this exhibition are a coherent group of well design compositions that colorfully and directly guide viewers through the creative explorations and visual explanations proffered by this innovative young artist.

The means employed in developing these visions are digital (computer based) tools that employ of some of the most esoteric contemporary methods of developing and elaborating images available to any artist. Dr. Tripti Singh works experimentally, yet fluently, with these digital tools weaving a powerful story that will deeply engage viewers through vivid colors, dramatic spatial relationships, and skeletal references to an enormous population of beings with whom viewers shares sentient steps along this artist's unique life-path.

I commend Dr. Tripti Singh for here efforts and predict that Amoghvarsha '12 is but the first of many outstanding digital art exhibitions that she will bring before the public in India – and beyond.

Dr. John Antoine Labadie

Fulbright Scholar & Professor of Art

Coordinator of Digital Arts & Media Integration Studies

Department of Art

University of North Carolina Pembroke

Pembroke, North Carolina USA

Message from: Prof. Margie Beth Labadie

When I met Tripti Singh she was student and a researcher. Now she is a teacher and artist who coming into her own with bold, visual statements which provide a new narration of who she is and who she wants to be. Tripti Singh is a unique digital artist with one foot in a world of great Indian tradition and another on the cusp of a growing art form that can travel electronically from machine to machine, and at times around the world, in seconds.

Tripti Singh's journey to gain an understanding of digital art forms has brought her to this moment of her first major art exhibition manifested in printed form. The imagery of her journey is evident in this exhibition. She expresses her struggles with life and her challenges as a female, as well as a digital artist in this fast growing, contemporary art field. Tripti's mastery of this computer based art form allows her to express universal questions of life, existence and hope. Emotions are expressed through form and pattern and are made evident in her uses of rich color. Each of the hundreds of tiny figures throughout her artwork can be considered as her thoughts moving along a path. Each figure, climbing ever upwards, joins hands in a movement toward this new place on a journey toward fulfillment. They are taking her to her own place in history as an Artist.

Tripti Singh's exhibition provides evocative, visual statements of an interior, complex world as she moves toward this new and better place. I applaud her in this artistic journey and congratulate her on this first solo exhibition.

Margie B. Labadie, MFA

Artist & Lecturer

University of North Carolina at Pembroke

Pembroke NC USA

Amoghvarsha '12'

Amoghvarsha '12' means Amogh means Ganesha, also it means “straight to the aim”. Varsha is “year” which is “2012”. From here my journey begins as this is my first solo show and it is aimed to reach maximum viewers who like to ask questions Who? What? Why? Where? How?

Amoghavarsha (Nrupathunga) (800–878 CE) was a Rashtrakuta emperor, the greatest ruler of the Rashtrakuta dynasty, and one of the great emperors of India. His reign of 64 years is the longest precisely dated monarchical reign on record in India and one of the longest documented reigns of any monarch. Historians have compared him to the legendary Emperor. He is said to have built the regal city to "match that of Lord Indra".

These artworks are delivered from struggle as an artist, researcher and as a woman. It feels it is like ovulation process where thousands of ideas fights to reach the mind to be created in physical form. The fittest were created and seen and felt as these artworks. It has been a painful process, many time the nerve was low, many times it was high... But whatever it was, it has to be continue to carry it, till it takes the birth and takes its own life.

This journey will lead to artistic perceptions of truth of life and search of a place where the life is celebrated, where the problems are handled by helping each other, where there is no gender bias not even issues like hunger, thrust, lust etc, where there is just a single goal to that is to continue this journey as it comes. This series of digital artworks' travels through numerous places that can match with the city of Amoghvarsha.

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas

While moving ahead saw a girl, she mesmerized me. I thought why not talk to her. She seems to be happy in this world. Standing alone with half closed eyes, it feels she is meditating on something. Asked her how was life before and what she experience in this world. She told "I have been struggling and burning inside to do the task in hand in that world. Many unfulfilled desires were achieved till target date as 12/12/2012... I accomplished most of them, still it feels something remaining and it is burning inside me"... I didn't ask what? Left her in search of other people to listen what they have to say.

Amoghvarsh 2

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival

Then I met an old woman who had wings, I asked how it feels to be here. She answered “I remember my struggle and my experience dealing with the world. I feel free in this world and I can fly. These people have hurt to that extent that I can still feel the pain of beaded wounds of my soul. It was struggle of survival I have lived long life. I had fought and never gave up. Just now these eggs caught my sight and I want to hatch them, I am ready to take more responsibility perhaps now life feels alive when it is burdened. I didn't ask her why she wants to get that burden when she is free from all..... I left and tried to search someone else.

Amoghvarsh 4

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

Here I came across bigger than life
monster I asked who are you? In
strange way he replied don't you know
me? We are companions of same path.
Sometime you overcome me sometime
I overcome you. We fight for our
existence can you feel you are strong
enough here to overcome me... I left it
don't want to know what it is trying to
say!

Amoghvarsh 5

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

Another creature but beautiful glowing with bright colours ... spreading some light around in which I can see people around. I asked what are you doing? He said don't you know me? I said no.. then he said you always ignore me or you are afraid to face me? Can't you see there are many people just like youlook around... then why you are ashamed ... why you are not accepting what you are.... I didn't asked what it means.... But left as they were.

Amoghvarsh 22

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

Strange path seems like lots of ups and downs. Asked that monster of that hidden gate what are you hiding? It said you need to look for it yourself.... If you have faith on you... you will get that way.... If you try you will win and if you will stay back you will lose. Choice is yours... I am doing my job to make it difficult for you to achieve.... You need to do what you feel to do.... I didn't ask why I need to know it. And left....

Amoghvarsh 10

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

Reached a great opening ...
magnificent view I asked myself
what is this place meant to be? Some
rituals are going on. It looks like
celebration of life..... What kind of
celebration? What is inside that
structure?

Amoghvarsh 13

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

I can see some structures floating in air... I can't feel what is underneath these structures. These structures have a passage and some people are inside these structures. What can be it? Where they are taking those people for what? Questions remain and I left the site.

Amoghvarsh 22

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

A magnificent view there is sense on the water but there is some surface under it which provide the surface to stand on. We are climbing the ropes to reach some other destination. I can see there are more exit points. Sometime I feel why I never get satisfied and why have to move on and on.

Amoghvarsh 11

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

We reached this place filled with water everywhere... we need to swim and reach to that exit point. The water is cristal clear and I can see the reflection of that structure standing with full might... somewhere I feel it is royal palace of an forgotton kingdom. But question is why I am here... and why can see it and feel it... do you feel same as I do?

Amoghvarsh 14

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

Simple things are toughest to explain they just appear in front and surprise oneself. May the complexity of thought and the brain creativity play with emotions. So we persive and we observe and we creatre... Sometime I am surprised by the feel of them do they exist in real do they mean something And enomours questions why this shape? Why this colour? Why these texture?

Amoghvarsh 17

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

The present site we are standing on some surface. I can feel the freedom in this un bound empty space. This gives me the joy to be with these strange people. I can see some ropes are hanging and people are climbing to reach some structure above. I want to touch it I want to be there and feel the structure from inside. Whats they purpose of it and why it is ment?

Amoghvarsh 18

122X153 cm

Digital Art

Amoghvarsh 19 Digital Art 2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

The pot with a water fall filling the water in a utencile with has some small outlets. The sound of water is the music that is making the surrounding more lively. The golden light and the golden structure feels the Hamam of the royal family.. I can see those baskets hanging from some where... and it feels we need to go there and take rest... for sometime....

Amoghvarsh 20

Digital Art

2012

Size 60"X48"

Print on Canvas Archival Quality

Those baskets with some ladders we have just came down from them.. it feels while we were taking rest they were moving and continuing our journey. I can see the change in the colour in those structures due to air fission.... Is it our faith to move on and on..... Where it will lead us....

Amoghvarsha 25 Medium: Digital Art Size 60"X48" Print on Canvas Archival Quality

An astonishing opening and a way to go on in some passage, we need to go inside and I am really very curious what it will be like?

Exhibitions:

1. Represented India in 10th December 2012 at Matrices 2012, 6th International Exhibition of Small Form Electrographic Art, Budapest, Hungary. Artwork included in permanent collection.
2. Participated in 1st United Art Fair 27- 30 September 2012
3. Artwork displayed in “India Day” held at “Multicultural Center” in the Old Main Building on 2 March 2011 UNCP Pembroke, North Carolina, USA.
4. Group Show 15-19 Nov 2009 in Renaissance Gallery Bangalore, featured a series on flowers.
5. Selection in International Artistic Linen Cloth Biennial 'Z krosna do Krosna' 2008 in Krosno, Poland.
6. Participation in Sguardi Sonori Festival of Media and Time Based Art, 2008. Selection among 33 countries' s 100 artist, Italy. Artwork included in permanent collection.

Publication and Critics:

1. 12/12/2012 published in <http://downtownlalife.tripod.com/id774.html> "Tripti Singh has mastered the digital medium so well that the very nuance of emotion and texture stands out with brilliant impact. These are wonderful examples of the new Indian digital art coming from Indian/ Punjabi/Rajasthan cultural artists. Her art is worthy of your personal collection and Tripti is going to make an important impact in the international art community." - Don Noyes-More, Editor in Chief, Downtown LA Life Magazine International, August 2012.
2. June 6, 2008 "Tripti Singh has mastered the digital medium so well that the very nuance of emotion and texture stands out with brilliant impact. The beautiful portraits of the four women (at left and below), are wonderful examples of the new Indian digital art coming from Indian/ Punjabi/Rajasthan cultural artists. Her art is worthy of your personal collection and Tripti is going to make an important impact in the international art community." - Don Noyes-More, Editor in Chief, Downtown LA Life Magazine.

Dr. **Tripti Singh**, “Creating these artworks been personal journey. It starts with conscious effort then carried away with the with the sheer thoughts to a particular destination and then art appears itself. I move silently from one to other artworks which depicts particular moment of my life and my struggle. I feel these artworks talk to me. They say what I feel, but many times different from the viewers.

Many times I get comments which are distinct from my story.

It feels seeds of thoughts grow in viewer’s receptive organs and it get processed and get connected with experiences. They become eager to tell their observations. As I heard these stories are based on some rituals of some distinct places on earth which viewers know and had experienced, whereas I never been those places and I didn’t know about it. So it is two way process. In this way it is very important for me to hear viewer’s stories.”

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